

Pword-report

Language name: **Khasi (LID 540)**
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Sources: Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com.
Rabel, Lili (1961) *Khasi, A Language of Assam*. Baton Rouge: Louisiana State University Press.
Date completed: 03.05.2006

I Language profile

of spks: 879'192 (1991 census)
place: India (Meghalaya, Assam, Manipur, West Bengal, Tripura states), Bangladesh
Contact lgs.: Bengali, Hindi, English, Assamese (all IE)
Status: official regional language in Meghalaya
Prospects: not endangered
Struct. results: -

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem
2. _____ Restricted pre-posed formative

NEG, TAM, AGR etc. are attached to V:

- | | | | |
|-----|---|-----|---|
| (1) | <i>ɲi-m-fɲ-ya-tip</i>
1p-NEG-NEG.PT-RECP-know
'We didn't know.' | (2) | <i>ɲa-n-ʔɲ-tʰoʔ</i>
1s-FUT-NEG-write
'I won't write.' |
|-----|---|-----|---|

3. _____ Semi-restricted pre-posed formative

Articles (so called in the grammar, <TG> I would prefer "a kind of noun class concord markers", although they are not obligatorily used on verbs. </TG>) can precede N, D, V, and the numeral 1:

(*ka*- 'fs' = FEM.SG, *ʔu*:- 'ms' = MASC.SG, *ʔi*:- 'ds' = DIM.SG, *ki*:- 'p' = PL)

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|-----|--|-----|---|
| (3) | <i>ka-wey ka-sɲi</i>
fs-1 fs-day
'one day' | (4) | <i>ki-kʰɲnaʔ ki-ba-rit</i>
p-child.PL p-REL-be.small
'the children who are small' |
|-----|--|-----|---|

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|-----|--|
| (5) | <i>ʔu-ni ʔu-tɲmen</i>
ms-DEM ms-old
'this old (man)' |
|-----|--|

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| (6) | <i>la-ka-ɲoɲ-ka-ɲiɲbuonkam ɲoɲ-ʔi</i>
OWN-fs-GEN-fs-business GEN-ds.PRON
'his _{SMALL} own business' |
|-----|--|

4. _____ Restricted post-posed formative

Numeral classifiers are only attached to numerals (only 2-99):

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|-----|---|-----|---|
| (7) | <i>ʔa:r-tʃli ki-miaw</i>
2-CLF p-cat
'two cats' | (8) | <i>sa:w-ɲut ki-briw</i>
4-CLF p-person
'four men' |
|-----|---|-----|---|

Certain adverblike suffixes are attached to verbs:

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|-----|---|
| (9) | <i>ya-ka-sɲi ru:ʔ ʔm-laʔ-yoʔ-ʔi:-fjuʔ</i>
PRIM-fs-sun also NEG-ABIL-get-look-NO.MORE
'(They) also could not see the sun any more.'
(PRIM = primary object, facultatively marked P = G) |
|-----|---|

- (10) *lej-lem*
go-TOGETHER
'to go together'

5. _____ Clause-final formative (Restricted to phrase, unrestricted to phonological host)

There are certain clause-final clitics, as =*ʔe:m* 'TAG.Q', =*ka* 'WORRY', =*siʔ* 'PLEASE', ...

- (11) *p^{hi}:-p^rk^hat-ʔaju:=ka*
2.HON-think.of(compound)=WORRY
'What's wrong with you?'
(without =ka: 'What are you thinking of?')
- (12) *ple:ŋ!* *p^{hi}:-ʔi:-k^huon* *ʔi:-klis=ʔe:m*
Surprise! 2.HON-ds-child ds-PN=TAG.Q
'Oh! You are the little son of Klis, right?'
- (13) *ruŋ~ruŋ=siʔ*
enter~INTENS=PLEASE
'Come in, please!'

→ 5 morpheme types

III Syllable

Syllable structure

- maximal syllable shape is (C)CCVVC
- VV can be long vowel or diphthong
- nucleus can be syllabic sonorant (m, n, ŋ, l, r) or schwa, but then only CÇ/Cə is possible!
- initial clusters have 2 C, only one word with 3 C's is attested: *spdok* 'short and stout' (in free var. with *su:pdok*)
- possible initial clusters:
 - Stop + Stop: *pt, pd, pj, pʔ; tb, td, tk, tʔ; kp, kb, kt, kt^h, kd, kj, kʔ; bt, bt^h, bd; dp, dk, dk^h; jk*
 - Stop + Fricative: *ks, kʃ; bs, bʃ; bh; jh*
 - Stop + Nasal: *pn, pŋ; p^hn, p^hŋ, p^hŋ; tm, tn, tŋ; t^hm, t^hn, t^hŋ; km, kn, kŋ; k^hm, k^hn, k^hŋ; bn, bŋ; dŋ; jm, jn, jŋ*
 - Stop + Liquid: *pl, pr; p^hl, p^hr; tl, tr; t^hl, t^hr; kl, kr; k^hl, k^hr; bl, br; jl, jr*
 - Stop + Glide: *tw; t^hw; kw, kj; k^hw; bj; dw; jw*
 - Fric. + Stop: *sp, sb, st, sd, sk, sk^h, sʔ; ft, fd, fk, fʔ*
 - Fric. + Nasal: *sm, sn, sŋ; fm, fn, fŋ*
 - Fric. + Liquid: *sl; jl, jr*
 - Fric. + Glide: *sw; fw*

(underlyingly also clusters of sonorants + C are possible, but a schwa is inserted to break up these clusters)

- (14) *k^hla* 'tiger'
briw 'person'
kmen 'happy'
sŋi: 'day, sun'
rənoŋ 'brass' (/rnoŋ/)

Monomoraic words

Monomoraic lexical words occur underlyingly, but the final vowel is optionally half-lengthened:

- (15) /k^hla/ → [k^hla(·)] 'tiger'

Monomoraic function words such as *ba* 'REL, DEM' or *ŋa* '1s' seem to be affixes.

Vowel-initial words

Not possible. There is at least a glottal stop: *?aspata:l* 'hospital'

But also non-initial syllables have to have an onset (one exception). Words like *kuon* 'child' are monosyllabic: [kɔ̃n]

→ σ-based restriction

The only exceptions are words with an i-final syllable followed by a u-initial syllable, such as *liur* [li:uɾ] 'rainy season', but possibly there is a glide inserted (not described in the grammar).

Polysyllabic morphemes

There are polysyllabic stems, but stems with 3 or more σ are mostly loans. Native bisyllabic words have in very most cases a syllabic sonorant or a schwa in the first syllable.

(16)	1 σ:	<i>k^hla</i>	'tiger'
	2 σ:	<i>kɾteŋ</i>	'name'
	3 σ:	<i>t^hamu:la</i>	'to be funny'
	4 σ:	<i>bajawala</i>	'bandsman'
	5 σ:	<i>k^hanasamari</i>	'census'

Phonotactics

- Syllables with syllabic sonorant consonants are not allowed to have complex onsets or a coda consonant.
- Nearly all syllables have an onset. The only exception is a u-syllable after i (see above).
- s, ʃ, h, l are disallowed in coda position (except in recent loans (*?asparagos* 'asparagus') and interjections)

Superheavy syllables

Only word-final syllables can be superheavy: *rwaay* [rəwa:j] 'to sing', *kper* [kpɛ:r] 'garden' (vowel is long due to the /ε/-lengthening before r), etc.

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

No tonal contrast is attested.

Stress

Primary stress is assigned to the final syllable of a word. Secondary stress is assigned in bisyllabic words to the first syllable, when it is heavy or has a syllabic consonant, and in trisyllabic words to the first syllable (independent from weight).

(17)	<i>kùmtá</i>	'thus'	(sec. stress, closed syllable → heavy)
	<i>ʃi:ní:</i>	'sugar'	(sec. stress, long vowel → heavy)
	<i>mḡtá</i>	'now'	(sec. stress, syll. consonant)
	<i>maré?</i>	'run'	(no sec. stress, first syllable light)
	<i>k^hànatáj</i>	'story'	(sec. stress on first syll. even though it is light)

If a prefix is attached, the whole complex is treated as a single word:

(18)	<i>ŋa-léj</i>	'1s-go'	'I go'
	<i>p^hi:-?óŋ</i>	'2p-say'	'you say'
	<i>ka-bríw</i>	'fs-person'	'a/the woman'

But, if a prefix is attached to a bisyllabic stem, the first syllable of the stem can keep its secondary stress:

(19)	<i>kà-bi:lór</i>	'fs-bottle'	'a/the bottle'
but:			
(20)	<i>kà-ʃa:-sá:w</i>	'fs-tea-black'	'black tea' (compound!)

Within words, all non-final syllables have a mid tone (³), where the final (stressed) one has a low falling pitch (²¹).

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

Ablaut

Ablaut is found in some reduplications, and always in quadruplication:

- (21) $k^hlij \sim k^hlij \sim k^hlij \sim k^hlij$ 'around and around'
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List of all phonological processes

1. Final stop neutralization (domain = σ)

$[-son, -cont] \rightarrow [-asp, -released] / ___ \sigma$

- (22) $/tip/ \rightarrow [tɪp̚]$ 'to know'
 $/riat/ \rightarrow [r̥iãt̚]$ 'precipice'
 $/miej/ \rightarrow [m̥e̝j̥t̚]$ 'table' (note, that there is no phoneme /c/ in the language)

2. Vowel insertion (domain = σ)

$\emptyset \rightarrow [ə] / (\sigma [+son] ___ C_{[-syllab]})$

- (23) $/lber/ \rightarrow [l̥əbɛ:r]$ 'March'
 $/mlien/ \rightarrow [m̥əl̥ɛ:ɛn]$ 'be accustomed to'
 $/rtan/ \rightarrow [r̥ət̥an]$ 'clingingly'

3. Vowel allophony rules (all have domain = σ)

Every vowel phoneme has certain allophones depending on onset and coda of the syllable in which it is situated. Since the phonemic character of some vowels is unclear, not all rules are given here. Only for illustration, the rules for /a/:

3a. $/a/ \rightarrow [ã] / i ___$

- (24) $/riat/ \rightarrow [r̥iãt̚]$ 'precipice'

3b. $/a/ \rightarrow [aː] / ___ \sigma$ (optionally)

- (25) $/k^hla/ \rightarrow [k^hlaː]$ 'tiger'

4. Vowel shortening

$/V:/ \rightarrow [-long] / ___ + ?C$

- (26) $/ʔuː-/$ 'ms' + $/ʔn/$ 'FUT' $\rightarrow [ʔun-]$ 'ms-FUT-' (glottal stop is deleted due to rule 5)

5. Glottal stop deletion (domain = σ , but at/across morpheme boundaries)

$/ʔ/ \rightarrow \emptyset$ $/ʔ+(\sigma ___)$
 $/V+(\sigma ___ C)$

- (27) $/joʔ/$ 'get' + $/ʔi:/$ 'look' $\rightarrow [joʔi:]$ 'see' (compound)

(N.B.: There is no degemination with other consonants: *matti*: 'finger joint', which is a compound of $/k^hmat/$ 'eye' + $/kti:/$ 'finger'. (Initial C's are sometimes, but not predictably, lost in compounding).)

- (28) $/ka-/$ 'fs' + $/ʔm-/$ 'NEG' $\rightarrow [kam-]$ 'fs-NEG-'
 $/ʔuː-/$ 'ms' + $/ʔn/$ 'FUT' $\rightarrow [ʔun-]$ 'ms-FUT-' (vowel is shortened due to rule 4)

\rightarrow Rules 4 and 5 together bring about a resyllabification.

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

All pre-posed particles are called free words, but since they always precede their host immediately, and since they participate in stress assignment (see section IV above), they have to be called prefixes. Additionally, there is some resyllabification, as shown in rules 4+5 above.

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

I did not find an affix that does not behave like the others concerning the above mentioned rules.

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Compounds show an interesting behaviour. Sometimes, but not predictably, initial consonants of initial clusters of the first part (rarely also of the second part) are dropped. There is one first compound part (*masi:* 'cow') losing a full vowel syllable (cf. (34)).

- | | | |
|------|---|---|
| (29) | /ka- k mat/ 'eye' + /liʔ/ 'white' | → ka-matliʔ 'the white of the eye' |
| (30) | /ka-lʔer/ 'wind' + /kʔllaŋ/ 'ʔ' | → ka-ʔe:rkʔllaŋ 'cyclone' (no loss of C's in the 2 nd part!) |
| (31) | /ʔir/ 'ʔ' + /ka- k mat/ 'eye' | → ka-ʔirmat 'eye lid(s)' |
| (32) | /ka-rnoŋ/ 'brass' + /stem/ 'be.yellow' | → ka-noŋtem 'yellowish brass' |
| (33) | /ka-pʔleŋ/ 'egg' + /ʔiw/ 'ʔ' | → ka-leŋʔiw 'bad smelling egg' |
| (34) | /ka- masi: / 'cow' + /k ^h ar/ 'ʔ' | → ka-si:k ^h ar 'interior cow imported from the plains' |

First parts of compounds can lose their inherent stress:

- (35) kà-ʃa:-sá:w 'fs-tea-black' 'black tea'

Sometimes consonants at the compound border assimilate and/or vowels of the first part are dropped (both optionally):

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|------|---|---|
| (36) | /k ^h uon/ 'child' + /luŋ/ 'be.young' | → k ^h uonluŋ ~ k ^h ŋluŋ ~ k ^h lluŋ 'young child, baby' |
| (37) | /wan/ 'go' + /lam/ 'bring' | → wanlam ~ wallam 'fetch' |

IX Reduplication

Two types of reduplication:

1. Indefinite pronouns can be formed by RED of a demonstrative or question word:

- (38) ka-ʔey~ka-ʔey
fs-Q~RED
'something'

2. Intensive adverbs can be formed by RED of a lexical word:

- (39) bla:p~bla:p
jabber~RED
'jabberingly'

Sometimes a syllable (without an isolatable meaning) is put between the reduplicants:

- | | | | |
|------|---|------|---|
| (40) | pateŋ-la~pateŋ
generation-ʔ~RED
'from generation to generation' | (41) | kaʔey-re~kaʔey
who-ʔ~RED
'something or other' |
|------|---|------|---|

There is no information whether or not reduplicated forms behave like a single word. Concerning intonation, they behave like a phrase or clause, cf. Section X below.

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

Phrases or declarative clauses have their highest pitch on the antepenultimate syllable. All syllables preceding this one, have a mid tone, the following two syllables fall in pitch.

- (42) *kat³.ta⁴.kat³.ta²¹* 'very much~RED'
(43) *k^hat³.da³.ka³.tɿ³.lut⁴.da³.sme:r²¹* 'drive away an evil spirit'

Sometimes this rule does not work in certain compounds:

- (44) *fi:³.teŋ³.sŋ³.na⁴--fi:³.teŋ³.dum³.mo²¹* 'midnight' (lit.: 'one half night, one half darkness')

Questions have either a sharp rise on the last syllable, or they keep their 21-pitch but then the antepenultimate syllable has "normal" mid intonation and the penultimate one has a 5 or 45 pitch.

- (45) *p^hi:³.kwa³.la⁵.yu:²¹?* 'You want what?'

There are two types of non-sentence-final clause intonations. One has a slightly falling pitch from the first (starting at 3) to the penultimate syllable (which has 1), but the last syllable is 3 again. (Sometimes the last syllable has 13 instead.) The other one has a straight 3 intonation:

- (46) *k^hat³.du³.k^hat³.way¹³,* *ka³.la³.lej³.yo³.li:³,* *lu:³.wey³ lu:³.dieŋ³so³.p^hi:³,*
finally fs-PT-go-get-look ms-1 ms-tree fruit
'Finally, she went and saw,, a tree with fruits,,
bat³ ka³.la³.kmen³, *ha³.du³.bom³.la³.loŋ³.fu²¹*
and fs-PT-be.happy until-NEG-PT-see-NO.MORE
and she was happy,, until she did not see it any more.'

If one part is a question, the Q-intonation overrides:

- (47) *p^hi:³.kwa³.da³.ka⁵.lej³,* *koŋ¹⁴?* 'You want of what, lady (=elder sister)?'

XI Other Special things

Geminates: occur, but never tautosyllabic, e.g. *wallam* 'to fetch' (compound: < *wan-lam 'go-bring')

Foot: No foot assignment rule is given in the grammar, but stress assignment leads to a iambic foot assigned from the right.